

Maximizing User Satisfaction in Wireless Networks with Integrated Aerial Base Stations

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Abstract Aerial base stations (ABSs) offer a practical means of expanding cellular network coverage. By incorporating ABSs, user equipment (UEs) can receive service when unable to connect to ground base stations (GBSs). Nevertheless, ensuring Quality-of-Service (QoS) satisfaction for all UEs, regardless of their serving base stations, is crucial. In this study, we address this challenge by formulating an optimization problem aimed at maximizing UE satisfaction within ABS integrated cellular networks. The defined problem is a mixed combinatorial and non-convex optimization problem and it is difficult to solve optimally in such a complex network environment. To tackle this, we propose a suboptimal heuristic dynamic scheduling algorithm that considers coordination between ABS and GBS. Numerical results demonstrate the effectiveness of our dynamic solution in terms of UE satisfaction compared to a baseline static algorithm, where QoS coefficients are initially set and remain unchanged throughout scheduling.

Keywords aerial base station · QoS · scheduling · cellular networks

1 Introduction

The main goal of the next-generation wireless networks is increased capacity with full communication coverage anywhere and anytime. To reach this target is not easy with conventional cellular networks since the number of mobile subscribers are increasing excessively day by day and it is expected to reach

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9.1 billion at the end of the 2028 [1]. Thus, in recent years, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technology has gained interest as a complementary solution to the conventional cellular networks to contribute reaching these targets. UAVs are foreseen an indispensable part of the future wireless communication networks because of the features like high flexibility with controllable mobility, on-demand deployment ability, high probability of having Line-of-Sight (LOS) communication links and ever-reducing cost [2–4].

UAVs can be used in different forms as relays [5–7], data collectors [8,9] or Aerial BS (ABS) [10–12] as a part of the wireless networks. The latter one offers several advantages such as eliminating coverage problem in certain areas (e.g., remote or hard-to-reach areas), capacity expansion in congested areas, or deployment on demand (which makes them ideal for temporary events or emergencies such as disaster response and emergency response). In this context, to obtain an enhanced wireless connectivity to personal and commercial ABS through mobile networks [13], there are ongoing standardization activities in 3GPP [14]. While working as an ABS to provide communication coverage to mobile users, two scenarios such as ABS alone communication coverage and ABS communication coverage together with existing Ground BS (GBS) can be examined [12]. There is no terrestrial infrastructure coverage for mobile users in the first scenario. Although, there are some terrestrial base stations in the second scenario, they cannot provide sufficient communications coverage for all mobile users so UAVs are located as an ABS to support the cellular network, improve communication coverage, and enhance the quality-of-service (QoS) of all mobile users.

Despite the advantages of utilizing ABS mentioned above, there are also many challenges to overcome. Among these challenges, optimal location of ABS [15–18], channel modeling [19,20], trajectory optimization [21–23], and network planning [11,24,25] have been explored in detail in the literature to reveal the potential of ABS in the next generation wireless networks. Additionally to these challenges, in practice, there can also be some other problems. First of all, ABSs (which can also be a fleet) are typically not part of the conventional cellular network infrastructure and are used for special applications, such as temporary coverage in disaster areas or for special events. Therefore, GBS initially is unaware of user information located under ABS coverage during deployment. Each ABS must be configured to reliably transmit user information such as location, signal strength, and device information when it connects to GBSs. GBSs then forward this information to the core network (CN) for further processing and routing to monitor network performance and troubleshoot problems. Second, GBS may not have direct control over the ABS and the User Equipments (UEs) connected to them. This makes it difficult to ensure both the required QoS requirements for differentiated users [26] and compliance with the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) of cellular services to be met. This may be due to various factors such as ABS mobility (which makes effective resource scheduling difficult), interference (which leads to scheduling conflicts), limited resources (battery, capacity, bandwidth), dynamic environment (prediction and scheduling obstacles due changing network

conditions), different and varying QoS requirements, and additional security and privacy measures to prevent cyber-attacks on cellular networks. Third, along with GBS, ABSs should also recognize different types of UEs that are connected and consider their priority requirements [27]. For example, if normal and premium UEs are present in whole cellular networks, normal UEs will have lower QoS requirements (e.g., lower data rate) than premium UEs. Therefore, normal UEs are satisfied with lower data rates, while premium UEs require higher data rates. These problems require an advanced coordinated scheduling approach between ABS and GBS that can improve user QoS requirements. The scheduling issue has also been studied as an optimization problem under different objective functions (capacity maximization, energy-efficiency maximization, etc.) and different constraints (QoS, power budget, fairness, etc.) for different system models [28–32]. In [28], the problem was defined as an energy-efficiency maximization problem considering the QoS requirements of the users for a Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) system model where only ABS served to the ground users. In [29], the problem was also formulated as an energy-efficiency maximization problem which takes into account the minimum QoS requirements of each user as in [28]. However, single cell network model used in [28] was extended to multicell network model which require the coordination of the multiple ABS. The problem was defined as minimum average throughput maximization and average secrecy rate maximization for Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA)-based ABS alone system model in [30] and [31], respectively. In [32], the optimization problem was formulated for maximizing the throughput by using the QoS constraint of the ground users and trajectory constraint of the ABS. However, all these studies focused on the ABS alone coverage system model that ignored the coordination of GBS and ABS.

In this paper, in contrast to the aforementioned studies that examine ABS alone network topology [28–32], we focus on the OFDMA based system model that provides ABS communication coverage together with existing GBS, which requires a strong coordination between ABS and GBS. We also concentrate on a different issue than the studies [10,21,24], which utilize an ABS and GBS integrated network model similar to ours. A literature summary is given in Table 1 to compare our study with existing ones in the literature. Moreover, a flowchart of the research process for this paper is given in Figure 1. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- The problem is formulated as maximizing the number of satisfied users while considering the QoS requirements of each ground user receiving service from either the GBS or ABS. To create a more realistic scenario, we incorporate different user types, such as normal and premium users, with varying scheduling rates.
- A heuristic solution is proposed to address this mixed combinatorial and non-convex optimization problem, which is difficult to solve optimally within such a complex network structure.

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM AND EXISTING RELATED
WORKS

Refs	Network	Focused problem	Access Technology	QoS Constraint
[10]	ABS-GBS integrated	Optimal ABS Placement	N/A	x
[21]	ABS-GBS integrated	Path planning	N/A	N/A
[23]	ABS alone	minimum average throughput maximization	OFDMA	✓
[24]	ABS-GBS integrated	Network planning	N/A	N/A
[28]	ABS alone	Energy-efficiency maximization	NOMA	✓
[29]	ABS alone	Energy-efficiency maximization	OFDMA	✓
[31]	ABS alone	secrecy rate maximization	OFDMA	x
[32]	ABS alone	secrecy rate maximization	OFDMA	✓
This paper	ABS-GBS integrated	Satisfied user maximization	OFDMA	✓

- The proposed scheduling scheme adjusts the scheduling rates for ABS and GBS users dynamically, unlike the static approach that maintains constant rates. This adaptive structure enables more efficient resource utilization.
- The proposed solution accounts for user priorities and establishes a coordination scheme between the GBS and ABS, thereby increasing the number of satisfied ABS users without compromising the satisfaction levels of GBS users.
- The advantages of our coordinated dynamic scheduling approach, compared to the static priority scheme, in terms of throughput and the number of satisfied users, are confirmed through numerical results in the context of the considered ABS-enabled cellular network scenario.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides the system model, concepts and problem formulation. Section 3 gives the details of the proposed tiered scheduling solution to the considered ABS-integrated problem. Section 4 gives the simulation setup details and numerical results. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and provides future work.

2 System Model and Problem Formulation

This section first introduces the network architecture and its components. Then, the models of the communication channels between the network nodes are formulated in detail in order to calculate the achievable data rates for each link. Finally, the optimization problem is outlined with its objective function and constraints.

Fig. 1: The research process flow of the paper.

2.1 Scenario Description

In this study, a downlink Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) OFDMA based system model, shown in Figure 2 is used. In this model, the UEs are located in the coverage area of the GBS. However, due to poor channel conditions, some of these UEs have very poor signal quality, which leads to connectivity problems with the GBS. To solve this problem, an ABS mounted on UAV is used to serve these UEs. The UAVs used for ABS can be fixed or rotary wing type. In our scenario, a rotary wing UAV is used and the ABS is assumed to serve UEs with poor signal quality for a period of time. ABSs can be directed to flexible locations in which cell-edge UEs are at high density. Figure 2 shows the connection between different types of UEs, ABS and the GBS. The connection method of the ABS to the GBS can be done via selected 3GPP radio relaying [33] assuming a line-of sight (LoS) visibility characteristics. The sampling technique approach in this paper is cluster sampling, where UEs are grouped into clusters based on geographical regions or network sectors, and entire clusters are sampled. This technique is particularly useful when analyzing performance in specific locations. It reflects the real-world clustering of UEs in areas such as stadiums, city centers, or remote locations, allowing for localized performance analysis of the scheduling algorithm.

There may be many criteria to distinguish UEs and provide different levels of service. Some may be based on QoS requirements (e.g., on latency, jitter,

Fig. 2: ABS-integrated cellular network and scheduling tiers with scheduling rates for normal, premium UEs and ABS.

data rate, where a user streaming a video may have different QoS requirements than a user using an instant messaging system), service types (such as video, voice, or data transmission), mobility characteristics (vehicular or pedestrian users), subscription types (prepaid or postpaid users), locations (urban, rural), terminal types (smartphone, tablet, laptop), or historical usage (peak hour or low hour user). Network slicing concept initiated in 5G systems can help provide such differentiated services for different priorities by dividing the network into multiple virtual networks [34]. In our scenario, the minimum required data rate is used as a QoS metric for different UE types. Other metrics such as signal strength, packet loss rates can also be used. However, the best approach depends on the specific needs of the network and the types of UEs it serves. In this paper, UEs are classified as normal and premium users according to their defined QoS metrics. UEs with higher required data rates are called premium and others are called as normal UEs. The amount of scheduling rates for premium UEs depend on the network capacity and the design choices of the Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) [26].

We assume that $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ is the set of all UEs including normal and premium UEs, served by GBS and ABS. \mathcal{K}^g represents the set of UE connected to the GBS, \mathcal{K}^a is the set of UE connected to the ABS, thus $\mathcal{K} = \mathcal{K}^g \cup \mathcal{K}^a$. Similarly, $\mathcal{K}_n^g \subset \mathcal{K}$ and $\mathcal{K}_p^g \subset \mathcal{K}$ are the sets of normal and premium UE connected to the GBS. $\mathcal{K}_n^a \subset \mathcal{K}$ and $\mathcal{K}_p^a \subset \mathcal{K}$ are the set of normal and premium UE connected to the ABS respectively. Note that, $\mathcal{K}_p = \mathcal{K}_p^g \cup \mathcal{K}_p^a$ and $\mathcal{K}_n = \mathcal{K}_n^g \cup \mathcal{K}_n^a$. A detailed list of symbols used throughout the paper is given in Table 2.

2.2 Data transmission

In this subsection, we will formulate the link achievable data rates between different nodes by presenting the channel models. The link achievable data rates via the connection can be calculated as;

TABLE 2
LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbol	Meaning
\mathcal{N}	Set of total nodes
\mathcal{M}	Set of RBs
\mathcal{M}^a	Set of RBs allocated to the ABS node in Tier 1 Scheduling
\mathcal{S}	Set of satisfied users
\mathcal{U}	Set of unsatisfied users
x	The rate of scheduling that is associated with a normal user
γ	The QoS coefficient for premium users
α	The QoS coefficient for the ABS

$$r_{i,j,m} = \frac{\mathcal{B}}{M} \log_2(1 + \gamma_{i,j,m}), \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{B} and M represents the total bandwidth of the system and number of resource blocks (RBs). In (1), $\gamma_{i,j,m} = \frac{\mathcal{P}_{i,j,m} h_{i,j,m}}{N_0 \frac{\mathcal{B}}{M}}$ is the signal to noise ratio (SNR) between any transmitter node i and receiver node j on RB m , $\mathcal{P}_{i,j,m}$ is the transmitted power per RB and $h_{i,j,m}$ is the channel gain between two nodes. The transmitter node i can be GBS or ABS and the receiver node j can be ABS or UE.

The channel gains mentioned above will be obtained in different ways according to the nodes used for the communication. If the communication is between two ground nodes like GBS to UEs, the channel is assumed to Rayleigh faded. In this case, the channel gain is modelled as $h_{i,j,m} = \frac{|g_{i,j,m}|^2}{(d_{i,j})^\zeta}$ where $d_{i,j}$ is the distance between transmitter node i (GBS) and receiver node j (any UE), ζ is the pathloss coefficient and $g_{i,j,m} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0,1)$ is the small-scale Rayleigh fading following a complex Gaussian distribution.

If the communication is between GBS to ABS or ABS to UE, the communication will be performed between air and ground. In [35], it has been validated that the air-ground channel is more likely to have the LoS link than the terrestrial ground-ground channels with the field trial. Thus, it is assumed that the wireless channel between these nodes are dominated by LoS channels as in the existing works [7, 36–39]. Thus, the channel gains between the GBS-ABS and ABS-UEs based on the free-space pathloss model can be modeled as $h_{i,j,m} = \frac{|d_{i,j}|^{-2}}{\left(\frac{4\pi f^m}{c}\right)^2}$ where f^m is the frequency of RB m , c is the velocity of light.

When the communication is between air and ground, the distance $d_{i,j}$ between transmitter node i and receiver node j is calculated by utilizing a three dimensional (3D) Cartesian coordinate system. The coordinates of the GBS, ABS and any UE can be selected as $(0, 0, 0)$, (x_{ABS}, y_{ABS}, H) and $(x_{UE}, y_{UE}, 0)$,

respectively. It is assumed that the ABS has an altitude H . Thus, the distance $d_{i,j}$ between transmitter node i (when it is GBS) and receiver node j (when it is ABS) is calculated as $d_{i,j} = \sqrt{(x_{ABS})^2 + (y_{ABS})^2 + H^2}$ and $d_{i,j}$ between transmitter node i (when it is ABS) and receiver node j (when it is UE) is calculated as $d_{i,j} = \sqrt{(x_{ABS} - x_{UE})^2 + (y_{ABS} - y_{UE})^2 + H^2}$.

2.3 Problem Definition

The main goal of this work is to maximize the number of satisfied users, whether they are connected to the GBS or the ABS. To achieve minimum required data rate values for all UEs, it is necessary to satisfy not only premium and normal UEs in GBS, but also those connected to ABS. In this way, MNOs can fulfill their obligations to the premium as well as normal UEs in terms of regulatory and consumer liabilities.

We introduce binary variables $\sigma \triangleq \{\sigma_j\}_{j \in \{\mathcal{K} \cup ABS\}}$ to label each receiver node includes UEs and ABS as satisfied or not as follows;

$$\sigma_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{receiver node } j \text{ is satisfied} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The value of σ_j is 1 if the condition $\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}^j} \lambda_{i,j,m} r_{i,j,m} \geq r_j^{min}$ is satisfied; otherwise σ_j is 0 where \mathcal{M}^j is the set of allocated RBs to node j and $\lambda_{i,j,m}$ is the binary RB assignment indicator. The QoS metric which is selected as the minimum required data rate in here can be defined as;

$$r_j^{min} = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if receiver node } j \text{ is normal UE} \\ \gamma x, & \text{if receiver node } j \text{ is premium UE} \\ \alpha x, & \text{if receiver node } j \text{ is ABS} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Based on above, the optimization problem that aims to maximize the number of satisfied users can be defined as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Maximize} && \sum_{j \in \{\mathcal{K} \cup ABS\}} \sigma_j, \\ & \text{subject to} && \begin{cases} (4.1) & \sigma_j \in \{0, 1\}, \forall j \\ (4.2) & \lambda_{i,j,m} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall i, j, m \\ (4.3) & \sum_j \sum_m \mathcal{P}_{i,j,m} \leq \mathcal{P}_i^{max}, \forall i \\ (4.4) & \mathcal{P}_{i,j,m} \geq 0, \forall i, j, m \\ (4.5) & \alpha > \gamma > 1 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In the given optimization problem, constraint (4.1) shows that σ is a binary variable defined to detect whether the receiver nodes are satisfied or not. Constraint (4.2) shows RB assignment indicator also takes binary values. The constraint (4.3) indicates that the total transmit power of GBS and ABS must not exceed the maximum power limit, \mathcal{P}_i^{max} where $i \in \{GBS, ABS\}$.

Constraint (4.4) guarantees that the transmit power cannot be negative and constraint (4.5) gives the relationship between the QoS metric coefficients α and γ . The problem defined in (4) is a mixed combinatorial and non-convex optimization problem, that is difficult to solve optimally at large scale. The network topology we are dealing with consists of multiple UEs, RBs and BSs. In this complex environment, it is even more difficult to solve the defined optimization problem. Therefore, in the next section, we present a suboptimal heuristic algorithm to solve the problem.

3 Proposed Tiered Scheduling Solution

In this section, the conventional scheduling procedure and the proposed coordinated scheduler are presented in detail.

3.1 Regular Procedure

In the network topology shown in Figure 2, before a UE can transmit User Plane (UP) data, it must establish a Control Plane (CP) signaling relationship with the Mobility Management Entity (MME) to obtain UP parameters including the predefined QoS Class Identifier (QCI) value assigned to its UP data stream [40]. After the UE obtains the assigned QCI value, it starts transmitting UP data in the Radio Access Network (RAN) with this assigned value. The scheduling rates for these QCI values are configured at GBS and at ABS. Since the ABS is connected to the GBS via the integrated access backhaul, the GBS does not know details about UEs that are connected to ABS and considers ABS as a single entity in its cellular network. Therefore, the GBS cannot determine the priority levels of the UEs connected to ABS which can be completely hidden from GBS. Note also that there could be several scheduling challenges in such ABS-integrated cellular systems, based on mobility, interference, limited resources, dynamic environment, QoS requirements.

A common technique for UE level minimum QoS guarantees in practical implementations is the assignment of pre-defined scheduling rates to the UEs by the CN. This process also depends on the UE detection procedure of GBS for different types of QCI values. In the conventional case, since RAN is aware of the established QCI value of the UP bearer and the previously configured schedule rates for the QCIs, the premium UEs are entitled to more schedules (time or frequency) than normal UEs in RAN. The main problem in a tiered structure of Figure 2 occurs when the scheduling rates assigned to ABS remain constant during operation of ABS. Due to the constant value of the scheduling rate for normal and premium users, a problematic situation may occur when new premium users are connected to ABS. In this case, premium users may receive less Resource Blocks (RBs) than normal users connected to GBS. This is undesirable for MNOs from regulatory perspective.

3.2 Proposed Coordinated Scheduler

In this subsection, we propose a heuristic two-tier scheduling algorithm to maximize the number of satisfied UEs in the considered cellular scenario to avoid the problems of traditional scheduling, that use the predefined scheduling rates, mentioned above. At the beginning of the coordination process, the GBS detects the presence of the ABS in the mobile network and assigns it the default QCI value. In Figure 2, the value x represents the scheduling rate associated with a normal UE. In addition, the coefficients α and γ indicate the assigned scheduling rates for ABS and premium users, respectively. These coefficients are set by individual MNOs according to their network structure [41]. During the coordination procedure between the GBS and ABS, the total number of connected users and their priority types (premium or normal) are reported through a coordination channel between the GBS and the ABS initiated by the Operation, Administration and Management (OAM) system in CN. The type of reporting may vary depending on the different types of UEs that are distinguished with defined QCI values. The details of the proposed procedure, described in *Proposed Algorithm*, are as follows;

The *Proposed Algorithm* in Algorithm 1 performs a tiered scheduling operation for GBS and ABS connected nodes, respectively. At the beginning of the algorithm, the QoS coefficients associated with the minimum required data rates of the receiver nodes (UEs and ABS) are specified. In Tier 1 scheduling (step (1)), RBs are allocated to the UEs and ABS considering the minimum QoS requirements. A *Satisfy QoS Requirements* function block (steps (6)-(15)) is used to perform this scheduling operation. This function first selects the receiver node with the highest QoS requirements (step (8)). Then the difference between the achievable link rates and the remaining data rate requirements of this receiver node is calculated over all suitable RBs (step (9)). Then, the RB that have minimum absolute difference is allocated to this node (step (10)). Finally, the QoS requirement of this node is updated and checked whether this node is satisfied or not (steps (11)-(13)). This process is terminated when all nodes are satisfied or all RBs are utilized. In Tier 2 scheduling (step (2)), the RBs allocated to the ABS are used to serve the UEs connected to ABS. The scheduling is performed with the same function block, *Satisfy QoS Requirements*. At the end of Tier 1 and Tier 2 scheduling, if all nodes connected to the GBS are satisfied but there are still unsatisfied UEs among the ABS users, the QoS coefficient α is increased to allocate more RBs to the ABS. With the new QoS coefficient, the scheduling is performed again for both tiers. The crucial point is to increase the number of satisfied UEs connected to the ABS without affecting the number of satisfied UEs connected to the GBS.

4 Numerical Results and Discussion

This section describes the simulation environment in detail, followed by a detailed presentation of the results and their discussion.

Algorithm 1 Proposed Algorithm**Initialization:**

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- Define minimum required data rates of each node, r_j^{min} as a QoS metric given in (3) by setting x , γ and α .
 - 1: Tier 1 Scheduling:
 - Set $\mathcal{M} = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$, $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{K}^g \cup \{ABS\}$
 - Set $\mu_j = r_j^{min}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}$, $\mathcal{S} = \emptyset$, $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{N}$.
 - Run function *Satisfy_QoS_Requirements()*.
 - $\mathcal{S}^{t1} = \mathcal{S}$ and $\mathcal{U}^{t1} = \mathcal{U}$
 - 2: Tier 2 Scheduling:
 - Set $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}^a$, $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{K}^a$.
 - Set $\mu_j = r_j^{min}$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}$, $\mathcal{S} = \emptyset$, $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{N}$.
 - Run function *Satisfy_QoS_Requirements()*.
 - $\mathcal{S}^{t2} = \mathcal{S}$ and $\mathcal{U}^{t2} = \mathcal{U}$
 - 3: **if** $\mathcal{U}^{t1} = \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{U}^{t2} \neq \emptyset$ **then**
 - Increase α value by one and Return to step 1.
 - 4: **else**
 - Terminate.
 - 5: **end if**
 - 6: **function** SATISFY_QOS_REQUIREMENTS()
 - 7: **while** $\mathcal{U} \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{M} \neq \emptyset$ **do**
 - 8: Find the receiver node, $j' = \arg \max_{j \in \mathcal{U}}(\mu_j)$
 - 9: Compute $r_{i,j',m}$ as in (1) by using equal transmit powers for j' , $\forall m \in \mathcal{M}$
 - 10: Find the RB, $m^* = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{M}} |r_{i,j',m} - \mu_{j'}|$ and $\mathcal{M} \leftarrow \mathcal{M} \setminus \{m^*\}$
 - 11: Update $\mu_{j'} = \mu_{j'} - r_{i,j',m^*}$
 - 12: **If** $\mu_{j'} < 0$ **then** $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \mathcal{S} \cup \{j'\}$, $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow \mathcal{U} \setminus \{j'\}$.
 - 13: Set $\lambda_{i,j',m^*} = 1$
 - 14: **end while**
 - 15: **end function**
 - 16: **end**
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4.1 Simulation Setup

In this section, numerical results are obtained to evaluate the performance of the proposed tiered scheduling algorithm for the defined optimization problem that aims to maximize the number of satisfied users. Data collection is performed in MATLAB environment which allowed us to simulate the environment, where parameters like UEs mobility, traffic loads, and interference levels can be carefully controlled and adjusted. Simulation enables the generation of relevant performance metrics, including signal strength, bandwidth usage, and network congestion. In our simulations, we set up a single cell system model as illustrated in Figure 3. A GBS is deployed in the center of the cell and

Fig. 3: System model

UEs are distributed around it. It is assumed that, because of an social event (concert, football match, etc.) or emergency situation, some of the UEs are clustered close to the cell-edge, where GBS can not serve them because of the heavy blockage. In this case, a rotary wing ABS is directed to this region and it is integrated to the cellular network to co-work with the GBS. It is seen from the Figure 3 that the ABS is deployed at an altitude, $H = 100$ m. This altitude selection is consistent with the existing literature [7,36,37] and fits the rule set by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) that in general, all commercial UAVs should not fly over 400 feet (122 m) [42]. Parameters from the 3GPP TS36.101 and TR36.814 standard are used in our simulations [43, 44]. The carrier frequency is set to 2 Ghz, the total bandwidth, \mathcal{B} is chosen as 20 Mhz with 100 RBs, and the noise power spectral density N_0 is -174 dbm/Hz. The maximum transmit powers for GBS and ABS are set to 46dBm and 35dBm, respectively. Simulation results are obtained by averaging 1000 Monte-Carlo trials. During simulations, we considered a fixed traffic type. Various traffic types such as periodic, aperiodic, non-deterministic, mixed can also be embedded into the proposed methodology. In our simulations, no multiple devices are trying to access the same channel at the same time. Each device transmits and receives data using different frequency band and no multiple devices are using the same band in order to avoid their transmissions interfere with each other. The remaining simulation parameters are detailed in Table 3.

TABLE 3
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
\mathcal{K}_n^g	10
\mathcal{K}_p^g	5
\mathcal{K}^a	2,4,6,8,10
\mathcal{K}_n^a	$\mathcal{K}^a/2$
\mathcal{K}_p^a	$\mathcal{K}^a/2$
Cell radius	750 m
Number of ABS	1
Antenna Configuration	1 × 1
Terminal Speed	3 km/h
x	1 Mbps
γ, α	1.5, 5
Path-loss exponent, ζ	4
Subframe Duration	1 ms
Simulation time	1 s

4.2 Evaluation Results

We compared the proposed tiered scheduling algorithm, which we also refer to as *proposed coordinated adaptive rate scheduling (PCARS)*, with the baseline algorithm in which the QoS coefficients are set initially and are not changed through the scheduling. When the bandwidth demand of all UEs increases, the baseline scheme which we also call *fixed rate scheduling (FRS)*, is no longer able to sufficiently serve to the connected users, especially the users connected to the ABS. The proposed scheme presents an adaptive scheduling by setting up a coordination mechanism between GBS and ABS, so the QoS coefficients can be updated according to the ABS requirements.

In Figures 4-6, the number of satisfied users (or UEs) meeting the minimum data rate requirements is compared for the proposed and the baseline schemes. In Figure 4, the number of satisfied ABS users is obtained by changing the number of users connected to the ABS. From this figure, it can be seen that the number of satisfied ABS users is significantly increased and it can be seen that the increase is more significant as the number of ABS users increases. For example, for a number of 6 ABS users, the proposed scheme yields of average 5.5 satisfied ABS users while the baseline scheme yields 2.1. This is achieved by increasing the QoS coefficient of ABS according to the requirements of the connected users in an adaptive manner under the coordination of GBS and ABS. However, while increasing the number of satisfied ABS users, it is also important not to decrease the number of satisfied GBS users to increase the total number of satisfied users in the cellular network. In Figure 5, it can be seen that the number of satisfied users for GBS is not affected. Thus, the positive impact of the proposed scheme is reflected in the total number of satisfied users, as shown in Figure 6. The provided results are significant because the scheduling rates are set in advance and do not change while ABS is in use. However, a potential issue may arise when new users join ABS in real-

Fig. 4: Number of satisfied ABS users

Fig. 5: Number of satisfied GBS users

Fig. 6: Total Number of satisfied users

world situations. These new users can not get required data rates. However, the proposed dynamic scheduling scheme provides a balance about sharing of the resources. With the proposed dynamic algorithm, the minimum data rates for GBS users are maintained and it is prevented that new users connecting to the ABS from suffering due to resource shortages by allowing for a reallocation of resources.

In Figures 7 and 8, the total data rate of each UE connected to the GBS and ABS is studied for baseline and proposed schemes. Simulation results are obtained for 15 GBS users (5 premium and 10 normal users) and 6 ABS users (3 premium and 3 normal users), as shown in Figures 7 and 8, respectively. The required data rate thresholds are used to highlight the normal and premium users connected to the GBS and ABS in these figures. The proposed scheme has significantly increased the data rate of both the premium and normal ABS users (Figure 8), while the data rate of GBS users has slightly decreased in relation to FRS (Figure 7). It is clear that this decrease in data rate for GBS users does not affect the number of satisfied GBS users. With the proposed scheme, a balancing mechanism is provided and by updating the QoS coefficient of ABS, the QoS requirements of all normal and premium users connected to ABS are satisfied as seen in Figure 8.

The computational complexity of two schemes is also compared in terms of average execution times in Figure 9. It is clear that increasing the number of satisfied users causes higher average execution times for the proposed scheme because of its dynamic nature. However, it is also clear that for 10 ABS connected users scenario, the number of satisfied users is increased almost 4

Fig. 7: GBS users total data rate

Fig. 8: ABS users total data rate

Fig. 9: Average execution times

Fig. 10: 95% CI for satisfied ABS users

Fig. 11: 95% CI for total number of satisfied users

times with a 1.4 times increment in the average execution time, which can be tolerable.

Finally, we calculated some statistical metrics such as the confidence interval (CI), which is crucial for a clearer and more reliable interpretation of the results. The CI results are shown in Figures 10 and 11. In Figure 10, we analyzed the performance of the baseline system and the proposed system based on the respective mean values of the number of satisfied ABS users and the 95% confidence intervals. This figure shows the results for 10 ABS users. The proposed scheme has a mean of 8.75, with a 95% CI ranging from 8.58 to 8.92, and the baseline scheme has a much lower mean of 2.37, with a 95% CI ranging from 2.22 to 2.52. The narrow range of CIs reflects the low variability and high precision of the data for both schemes. The mean value of the proposed scheme is much higher than the mean value of the baseline scheme, illustrating a significant improvement in performance. The 95% CIs for the two schemes do not overlap and this non-overlap strongly suggests that the difference in means is statistically significant, indicating that the proposed scheme is consistently superior to the baseline scheme. We also analyzed the performance of the baseline and the proposed system by using their respective mean values of the total number of satisfied users and 95% confidence intervals in Figure 11. To obtain the results, the total number of users in the network is set to 25. The proposed scheme has a mean of 22.88, accompanied by a 95% con-

confidence interval ranging from 22.58 to 23.17, while the baseline scheme has a significantly lower mean of 16.49, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 16.30 to 16.68. Both systems have narrow confidence intervals, indicating that the results are reliable. As a result, the proposed scheme clearly outperforms the baseline scheme, as evidenced by the significantly higher mean and non-overlapping confidence intervals. These results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach, which shows a statistically significant improvement over the baseline scheme.

5 Conclusions

In this study, we examined an ABS-integrated OFDMA-based cellular network topology, assuming that some UEs may encounter connectivity issues with the GBS due to adverse channel conditions. We formulated an optimization problem to maximize the number of satisfied UEs, regardless of whether they connect to the GBS or ABS. Minimum required data rate is used as a QoS metric to assess UEs satisfaction. The problem defined is a mixed combinatorial and non-convex optimization issue, making it challenging to solve optimally within this complex network environment. Thus, we propose a sub-optimal solution to tackle this problem. The proposed scheduling algorithm is in a dynamic nature that facilitates coordination between the GBS and ABS, in contrast to the static scheduling methods typically used in practice. Our numerical results confirm that the proposed approach meets QoS requirements for both GBS and ABS users across various priority levels, outperforming the baseline scheme with a tolerable computational complexity increment. For future work, we plan to address the defined scheduling problem using machine learning techniques. We also intend to extend the analysis to take into account different data rates and scenarios with multiple antennas.

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Data Availability Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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